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Abstract. *The aim of this article is to thoroughly investigate the theme "The category of person" and reveal its specific grammatical, pragmatic, stylistic, lexical and semantic peculiarities. Also I aimed at analysing the use of the category of person in the literary work "Love of life" by Jack London. This way we intend to survey the use of person in a literary work by a definite author and reveal his writing style.*

Key words: *specific grammatical, pragmatic, stylistic, lexical and semantic peculiarities.*

ПРЕПОДАВАТЕЛЬ КАФЕДРЫ ИСТОРИИ И ФИЛОЛОГИИ АЗИАТСКОГО
МЕЖДУНАРОДНОГО УНИВЕРСИТЕТА.

Аннотация. *Целью данной статьи является детальное исследование темы «Категория человека» и выявление ее специфических грамматических, прагматических, стилистических, лексических и семантических особенностей. Также я поставил перед собой задачу проанализировать использование категории человека в произведении Джека Лондона «Любовь к жизни». Таким образом мы намерены рассмотреть использование лица в литературном произведении конкретного автора и выявить его стиль письма.*

Ключевые слова: *специфические грамматические, прагматические, стилистические, лексические и семантические особенности.*

Introduction

John Griffith London (born John Griffith Chaney; January 12, 1876 – November 22, 1916) was an American novelist, journalist, and social activist. A pioneer in the world of commercial magazine fiction, he was one of the first writers to become a worldwide celebrity and earn a large fortune from writing. He was also an innovator in the genre that would later become known as science fiction. His most famous works include *The Call of the Wild* and *White Fang*, both set in the Klondike Gold Rush, as well as the short stories "To Build a Fire", "An Odyssey of the North", and "Love of Life". He also wrote about the South Pacific in stories such as "The Pearls of Parlay", and "The Heathen".⁰

London was part of the radical literary group "The Crowd" in San Francisco and a passionate advocate of unionization, workers' rights, socialism, and eugenics.^{[7][8]} He wrote several works dealing with these topics, such as his dystopian novel *The Iron Heel*, his non-fiction exposé *The People of the Abyss*, *The War of the Classes*, and *Before Adam*.

Family

Flora Wellman

Jack London's mother, Flora Wellman, was the fifth and youngest child of Pennsylvania Canal builder Marshall Wellman and his first wife, Eleanor Garrett Jones. Marshall Wellman was descended from Thomas Wellman, an early Puritan settler in the Massachusetts Bay Colony. Flora left Ohio and moved to the Pacific coast when her father remarried after her mother died. In San Francisco, Flora worked as a music teacher and spiritualist, claiming to channel the spirit of a Sauk chief, Black Hawk. Biographer Clarice Stasz and others believe London's father was astrologer William Chaney. Flora Wellman was living with Chaney in San Francisco when she became

pregnant. Whether Wellman and Chaney were legally married is unknown. Stasz notes that in his memoirs, Chaney refers to London's mother Flora Wellman as having been "his wife"; he also cites an advertisement in which Flora called herself "Florence Wellman Chaney".

According to Flora Wellman's account, as recorded in the San Francisco Chronicle of June 4, 1875, Chaney demanded that she have an abortion. When she refused, he disclaimed responsibility for the child. In desperation, she shot herself. She was not seriously wounded, but she was temporarily deranged. After giving birth, Flora turned the baby over for care to Virginia Prentiss, an African-American woman and former slave. She was a major maternal figure throughout London's life. Late in 1876, Flora Wellman married John London, a partially disabled Civil War veteran, and brought her baby John, later known as Jack, to live with the newly married couple. The family moved around the San Francisco Bay Area before settling in Oakland, where London completed public grade school.

In 1897, when he was 21 and a student at the University of California, Berkeley, London searched for and read the newspaper accounts of his mother's suicide attempt and the name of his biological father. He wrote to William Chaney, then living in Chicago. Chaney responded that he could not be London's father because he was impotent; he casually asserted that London's mother had relations with other men and averred that she had slandered him when she said he insisted on an abortion. Chaney concluded by saying that he was more to be pitied than London. London was devastated by his father's letter; in the months following, he quit school at Berkeley and went to the Klondike during the gold rush boom.

Early life

London at the age of nine with his dog Rollo, 1885

London was born near Third and Brannan Streets in San Francisco. The house burned down in the fire after the 1906 San Francisco earthquake; the California Historical Society placed a plaque at the site in 1953. Although the family was working class, it was not as impoverished as London's later accounts claimed. London was largely self-educated.

In 1885, London found and read Ouida's long Victorian novel *Signa*. He credited this as the seed of his literary success.[16] In 1886, he went to the Oakland Public Library and found a sympathetic librarian, Ina Coolbrith, who encouraged his learning. (She later became California's first poet laureate and an important figure in the San Francisco literary community).

In 1889, London began working 12 to 18 hours a day at Hickmott's Cannery. Seeking a way out, he borrowed money from his foster mother Virginia Prentiss, bought the sloop *Razzle-Dazzle* from an oyster pirate named French Frank, and became an oyster pirate himself. In his memoir, *John Barleycorn*, he claims also to have stolen French Frank's mistress Mamie. After a few months, his sloop became damaged beyond repair. London hired on as a member of the California Fish Patrol.

In 1893, he signed on to the sealing schooner *Sophie Sutherland*, bound for the coast of Japan. When he returned, the country was in the grip of the panic of '93 and Oakland was swept by labor unrest. After grueling jobs in a jute mill and a street-railway power plant, London joined Coxey's Army and began his career as a tramp. In 1894, he spent 30 days for vagrancy in the Erie County Penitentiary at Buffalo, New York. In *The Road*, he wrote:

Man-handling was merely one of the very minor unprintable horrors of the Erie County Pen. I say 'unprintable'; and in justice I must also say undescrivable. They were unthinkable to me

until I saw them, and I was no spring chicken in the ways of the world and the awful abysses of human degradation. It would take a deep plummet to reach bottom in the Erie County Pen, and I do but skim lightly and facetiously the surface of things as I there saw them.

Gold rush and first success

Miners and prospectors ascend the Chilkoot Trail during the Klondike Gold Rush

On July 12, 1897, London (age 21) and his sister's husband Captain Shepard sailed to join the Klondike Gold Rush. This was the setting for some of his first successful stories. London's time in the harsh Klondike, however, was detrimental to his health. Like so many other men who were malnourished in the goldfields, London developed scurvy. His gums became swollen, leading to the loss of his four front teeth. A constant gnawing pain affected his hip and leg muscles, and his face was stricken with marks that always reminded him of the struggles he faced in the Klondike. Father William Judge, "The Saint of Dawson", had a facility in Dawson that provided shelter, food and any available medicine to London and others. His struggles there inspired London's short story, "To Build a Fire" (1902, revised in 1908), which many critics assess as his best.

His landlords in Dawson were mining engineers Marshall Latham Bond and Louis Whitford Bond, educated at the Bachelor's level at the Sheffield Scientific School at Yale and at the Master's level at Stanford, respectively. The brothers' father, Judge Hiram Bond, was a wealthy mining investor. While the Bond brothers were at Stanford Hiram at the suggestion of his brother bought the New Park Estate at Santa Clara as well as a local bank. The Bonds, especially Hiram, were active Republicans. Marshall Bond's diary mentions friendly sparring with London on political issues as a camp pastime.[citation needed]

London left Oakland with a social conscience and socialist leanings; he returned to become an activist for socialism. He concluded that his only hope of escaping the work "trap" was to get an education and "sell his brains". He saw his writing as a business, his ticket out of poverty, and, he hoped, a means of beating the wealthy at their own game. On returning to California in 1898, London began working to get published, a struggle described in his novel, *Martin Eden* (serialized in 1908, published in 1909). His first published story since high school was "To the Man On Trail", which has frequently been collected in anthologies.[citation needed] When *The Overland Monthly* offered him only five dollars for it—and was slow paying—London came close to abandoning his writing career. In his words, "literally and literarily I was saved" when *The Black Cat* accepted his story "A Thousand Deaths", and paid him \$40—the "first money I ever received for a story". London began his writing career just as new printing technologies enabled lower-cost production of magazines. This resulted in a boom in popular magazines aimed at a wide public audience and a strong market for short fiction.[citation needed] In 1900, he made \$2,500 in writing, about \$77,000 in today's currency.[citation needed] Among the works he sold to magazines was a short story known as either "Diable" (1902) or "Bâtard" (1904), two editions of the same basic story; London received \$141.25 for this story on May 27, 1902. In the text, a cruel French Canadian brutalizes his dog, and the dog retaliates and kills the man. London told some of his critics that man's actions are the main cause of the behavior of their animals, and he would show this in another story, *The Call of the Wild*. George Sterling, Mary Austin, Jack London, and Jimmie Hopper on the beach at Carmel, California

In early 1903, London sold *The Call of the Wild* to *The Saturday Evening Post* for \$750, and the book rights to Macmillan for \$2,000. Macmillan's promotional campaign propelled it to swift success. While living at his rented villa on Lake Merritt in Oakland, California, London met poet George Sterling; in time they became best friends. In 1902, Sterling helped London find a home closer to his own in nearby Piedmont. In his letters London addressed Sterling as "Greek", owing to Sterling's aquiline nose and classical profile, and he signed them as "Wolf". London was later to depict Sterling as Russ Brissenden in his autobiographical novel *Martin Eden* (1910) and as Mark Hall in *The Valley of the Moon* (1913).

In later life London indulged his wide-ranging interests by accumulating a personal library of 15,000 volumes. He referred to his books as "the tools of my trade". London spent \$80,000 (\$2,280,000 in current value) to build a 15,000-square-foot (1,400 m²) stone mansion called Wolf House on the property. Just as the mansion was nearing completion, two weeks before the Londons planned to move in, it was destroyed by fire. London's last visit to Hawaii,^[53] beginning in December 1915, lasted eight months. He met with Duke Kahanamoku, Prince Jonah Kūhiō Kalaniana'ole, Queen Lili'uokalani and many others, before returning to his ranch in July 1916. He was suffering from kidney failure, but he continued to work.

First marriage (1900–1904)

London married Elizabeth "Bessie" Maddern on April 7, 1900, the same day *The Son of the Wolf* was published. Bess had been part of his circle of friends for a number of years. She was related to stage actresses Minnie Maddern Fiske and Emily Stevens. Stasz says, "Both acknowledged publicly that they were not marrying out of love, but from friendship and a belief that they would produce sturdy children."^[30] Kingman says, "they were comfortable together... Jack had made it clear to Bessie that he did not love her, but that he liked her enough to make a successful marriage."

London met Bessie through his friend at Oakland High School, Fred Jacobs; she was Fred's fiancée. Bessie, who tutored at Anderson's University Academy in Alameda California, tutored Jack in preparation for his entrance exams for the University of California at Berkeley in 1896. Jacobs was killed aboard the *USAT Scandia* in 1897, but Jack and Bessie continued their friendship, which included taking photos and developing the film together. This was the beginning of Jack's passion for photography.

During the marriage, London continued his friendship with Anna Strunsky, co-authoring *The Kempton-Wace Letters*, an epistolary novel contrasting two philosophies of love. Anna, writing "Dane Kempton's" letters, arguing for a romantic view of marriage, while London, writing "Herbert Wace's" letters, argued for a scientific view, based on Darwinism and eugenics. In the novel, his fictional character contrasted two women he had known.

London's pet name for Bess was "Mother-Girl" and Bess's for London was "Daddy-Boy". Their first child, Joan, was born on January 15, 1901, and their second, Bessie (later called Becky), on October 20, 1902. Both children were born in Piedmont, California. Here London wrote one of his most celebrated works, *The Call of the Wild*.

While London had pride in his children, the marriage was strained. Kingman says that by 1903 the couple were close to separation as they were "extremely incompatible". "Jack was still so kind and gentle with Bessie that when Cloudsley Johns was a house guest in February 1903 he didn't suspect a breakup of their marriage."

London reportedly complained to friends Joseph Noel and George Sterling:

[Bessie] is devoted to purity. When I tell her morality is only evidence of low blood pressure, she hates me. She'd sell me and the children out for her damned purity. It's terrible. Every time I come back after being away from home for a night she won't let me be in the same room with her if she can help it.

Stasz writes that these were "code words for fear that was consorting with prostitutes and might bring home venereal disease."

On July 24, 1903, London told Bessie he was leaving and moved out. During 1904, London and Bess negotiated the terms of a divorce, and the decree was granted on November 11, 1904.

War correspondent (1904)

London accepted an assignment of the San Francisco Examiner to cover the Russo-Japanese War in early 1904, arriving in Yokohama on January 25, 1904. He was arrested by Japanese authorities in Shimonoseki, but released through the intervention of American ambassador Lloyd Griscom. After travelling to Korea, he was again arrested by Japanese authorities for straying too close to the border with Manchuria without official permission, and was sent back to Seoul. Released again, London was permitted to travel with the Imperial Japanese Army to the border, and to observe the Battle of the Yalu.

London asked William Randolph Hearst, the owner of the San Francisco Examiner, to be allowed to transfer to the Imperial Russian Army, where he felt that restrictions on his reporting and his movements would be less severe. However, before this could be arranged, he was arrested for a third time in four months, this time for assaulting his Japanese assistants, whom he accused of stealing the fodder for his horse. Released through the personal intervention of President Theodore Roosevelt, London departed the front in June 1904.

Second marriage

After divorcing Maddern, London married Charmian Kittredge in 1905. London had been introduced to Kittredge in 1900 by her aunt Netta Eames, who was an editor at Overland Monthly magazine in San Francisco. The two met prior to his first marriage but became lovers years later after Jack and Bessie London visited Wake Robin, Netta Eames' Sonoma County resort, in 1903. London was injured when he fell from a buggy, and Netta arranged for Charmian to care for him. The two developed a friendship, as Charmian, Netta, her husband Roscoe, and London were politically aligned with socialist causes. At some point the relationship became romantic, and Jack divorced his wife to marry Charmian, who was five years his senior.

Biographer Russ Kingman called Charmian "Jack's soul-mate, always at his side, and a perfect match." Their time together included numerous trips, including a 1907 cruise on the yacht Snark to Hawaii and Australia. Many of London's stories are based on his visits to Hawaii, the last one for 10 months beginning in December 1915.

The couple also visited Goldfield, Nevada, in 1907, where they were guests of the Bond brothers, London's Dawson City landlords. The Bond brothers were working in Nevada as mining engineers.

London had contrasted the concepts of the "Mother Girl" and the "Mate Woman" in The Kempton-Wace Letters. His pet name for Bess had been "Mother-Girl;" his pet name for Charmian was "Mate-Woman." Charmian's aunt and foster mother, a disciple of Victoria Woodhull, had raised her without prudishness. Every biographer alludes to Charmian's uninhibited sexuality.

The Snark in Australia, 1921

Joseph Noel calls the events from 1903 to 1905 "a domestic drama that would have intrigued the pen of an Ibsen.... London's had comedy relief in it and a sort of easy-going romance." In broad outline, London was restless in his first marriage, sought extramarital sexual affairs, and found, in Charmian Kittredge, not only a sexually active and adventurous partner, but his future life-companion. They attempted to have children; one child died at birth, and another pregnancy ended in a miscarriage.

In 1906, London published in Collier's magazine his eye-witness report of the San Francisco earthquake.

Death

London died November 22, 1916, in a sleeping porch in a cottage on his ranch. London had been a robust man but had suffered several serious illnesses, including scurvy in the Klondike. Additionally, during travels on the Snark, he and Charmian picked up unspecified tropical infections and diseases, including yaws. At the time of his death, he suffered from dysentery, late-stage alcoholism, and uremia; he was in extreme pain and taking morphine. London's ashes were buried on his property not far from the Wolf House. London's funeral took place on November 26, 1916, attended only by close friends, relatives, and workers of the property. In accordance with his wishes, he was cremated and buried next to some pioneer children, under a rock that belonged to the Wolf House. After Charmian's death in 1955, she was also cremated and then buried with her husband in the same spot that her husband chose. The grave is marked by a mossy boulder. The buildings and property were later preserved as Jack London State Historic Park, in Glen Ellen, California.

Suicide debate

Because he was using morphine, many older sources describe London's death as a suicide, and some still do. This conjecture appears to be a rumor, or speculation based on incidents in his fiction writings. His death certificate gives the cause as uremia, following acute renal colic.

The biographer Stasz writes, "Following London's death, for a number of reasons, a biographical myth developed in which he has been portrayed as an alcoholic womanizer who committed suicide. Recent scholarship based upon firsthand documents challenges this caricature." Most biographers, including Russ Kingman, now agree he died of uremia aggravated by an accidental morphine overdose.

London's fiction featured several suicides. In his autobiographical memoir *John Barleycorn*, he claims, as a youth, to have drunkenly stumbled overboard into the San Francisco Bay, "some maundering fancy of going out with the tide suddenly obsessed me". He said he drifted and nearly succeeded in drowning before sobering up and being rescued by fishermen. In the dénouement of *The Little Lady of the Big House*, the heroine, confronted by the pain of a mortal gunshot wound, undergoes a physician-assisted suicide by morphine. Also, in *Martin Eden*, the principal protagonist, who shares certain characteristics with London, drowns himself.

Short stories

London's "strength of utterance" is at its height in his stories, and they are painstakingly well-constructed.[citation needed] "To Build a Fire" is the best known of all his stories. Set in the harsh Klondike, it recounts the haphazard trek of a new arrival who has ignored an old-timer's warning about the risks of traveling alone. Falling through the ice into a creek in seventy-five-

below weather, the unnamed man is keenly aware that survival depends on his untested skills at quickly building a fire to dry his clothes and warm his extremities. After publishing a tame version of this story—with a sunny outcome—in *The Youth's Companion* in 1902, London offered a second, more severe take on the man's predicament in *The Century Magazine* in 1908. Reading both provides an illustration of London's growth and maturation as a writer. As Labor (1994) observes: "To compare the two versions is itself an instructive lesson in what distinguished a great work of literary art from a good children's story."

London's most famous novels are "The Call of the Wild", "White Fang", "The Sea-Wolf", "The Iron Heel", and "Martin Eden".

In a letter dated December 27, 1901, London's Macmillan publisher George Platt Brett, Sr., said "he believed Jack's fiction represented 'the very best kind of work' done in America."

Critic Maxwell Geismar called *The Call of the Wild* "a beautiful prose poem"; editor Franklin Walker said that it "belongs on a shelf with *Walden* and *Huckleberry Finn*"; and novelist E.L. Doctorow called it "a mordant parable ... his masterpiece."

The historian Dale L. Walker commented:

Jack London was an uncomfortable novelist, that form too long for his natural impatience and the quickness of his mind. His novels, even the best of them, are hugely flawed.

Novels

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Some critics have said that his novels are episodic and resemble linked short stories. Dale L. Walker writes:

The Star Rover, that magnificent experiment, is actually a series of short stories connected by a unifying device ... *Smoke Bellew* is a series of stories bound together in a novel-like form by their reappearing protagonist, *Kit Bellew*; and *John Barleycorn* ... is a synoptic series of short episodes.

About "Love of Life"

Jack London's short story, "Love of Life" is about two gold prospectors, Bill and an unnamed man, who are struggling to survive on the frozen tundra of Canada. They cross the tundra looking for food, all the while suffering from starvation and exposure to the elements. When the unnamed man sprains his ankle, Bill abandons him and proceeds through the wilderness, his will to survive put to the test.

The tables are turned in the story when it appears that Bill has been killed by the elements, having carried his sack of gold with him until the very end. The man who sprained his ankle comes upon him in the wilderness, but neglects to take the gold with him. He ultimately resorts to

crawling across the tundra, devoid of any weapons. After surviving a wolf attack, he is discovered, semi-conscious, by a group of explorers traveling by ship. He recovers while on the ship, and is brought back to health.

This is a story of survival at its most pure. It is an exploration of a man's will to survive. London tells the story in great detail, recounting moments of fear, anguish and raw hunger endured by his protagonists.

**The analysis of the use of grammatical category of Person in the story
“Love of life” written by Jack London**

In this part of our course paper we are going to analyse the use of The category of person in the following examples which were taken from the story:

1.They were tired and weak, and their faces had the drawn expression of patience which comes of hardship long endured.

2. It was not the fear that he should die passively from lack of food, but that he should be destroyed violently before starvation had exhausted the last particle of the endeavor in him that made toward surviving.

3.His voice was utterly and drearily expressionless. He spoke without enthusiasm; and the first man, limping into the milky stream that foamed over the rocks, vouchsafed no reply.

4. . Farther on he knew he would come to where dead spruce and fir, very small and weazened, bordered the shore of a little lake, the titchin-nichilie, in the tongue of the country, the "land of little sticks." And into that lake flowed a small stream, the water of which was not milky.

5. The blanket socks were worn through in places, and his feet were raw and bleeding. His ankle was throbbing, and he gave it an examination.

6. As he rolled over on his elbow he was startled by a loud snort, and saw a bull caribou regarding him with alert curiosity.

7. There were no trees, no bushes, nothing but a gray sea of moss scarcely diversified by gray rocks, gray lakelets, and gray streamlets. The sky was gray. There was no sun nor hint of sun.

8. Soon he would come to the land of the little sticks. He felt that it lay off to the left somewhere, not far -- possibly just over the next low hill.

9. He could hide it under his two hands. He knew that it weighed fifteen pounds, -- as much as all the rest of the pack, -- and it worried him. He finally set it to one side and proceeded to roll the pack.

10. He picked it up hastily with a defiant glance about him, as though the desolation were trying to rob him of it; and when he rose to his feet to stagger on into the day, it was included in the pack on his back.

11. If the man ran, he would run after him; but the man did not run. He was animated now with the courage of fear.

12. It was unreasonable that he should die after all he had undergone

13. When he finally gained his feet, another minute or so was consumed in straightening up, so that he could stand erect as a man should stand.

14. How could he have the laugh on Bill if that were Bill; if those bones, so pinky-white and clean, were Bill?

15. So much of the game will be gain,

Though the gold of the dice has been lost."

Analysis

1. They weretired and weak, and their faces had the drawn expression of patience which comes of hardship long endured.

were- Verbal lexeme in plural form in the past Indefinite tense. The verb were has separate forms in the Past Indefinite to indicate person. In this sentence it comes with “they” (the third-person pronoun). It is second subsystem of the category of person.

Comes- The ending -s in the verb of come is the marker of the third person singular in the Present Indefinite Indicative, while the other forms have no ending. This inflexion -s signified that the subject of the sentence has to be a noun in singular, which correlates with a third person pronoun.

2. It was not the fear that he should die passively from lack of food, but that he should be destroyed violently before starvation had exhausted the last particle of the endeavor in him that made toward surviving.

He, It-third-person singular

Was- Verbal lexeme in singular in the past tense. In this sentence it comes with “It” (the third-person pronoun). It is second subsystem of the category of person. The verb has separate forms in the Past Indefinite to indicate person.

Should- In this sentence “should” comes as the auxiliary verb. Moreover, should can be used with the first person. In contrast, In this sentence it comes with “he” which is the third-person pronoun.

3. His voice was utterly and drearily expressionless. He spoke without enthusiasm; and the first man, limping into the milky stream that foamed over the rocks, vouchsafed no reply.

His- Possessive determiner. It showed distinctions in person in this sentence. “his” is placed in front of the noun it modify (VOICE)

Was- Verbal lexeme in singular in the past tense. In this sentence it comes with the noun “voice” It is second subsystem of the category of person. The verb has separate forms in the Past Indefinite to indicate person.

He-third-person singular

4. Farther on he knew he would come to where dead spruce and fir, very small and weazened, bordered the shore of a little lake, the titchin-nichilie, in the tongue of the country, the "land of little sticks." And into that lake flowed a small stream, the water of which was not milky.

He-third-person singular in this sentence.

Would- In this sentence “would” comes as the auxiliary verb and modal verb. While “would” can be used with all the persons. It refers to first subsystem of the category of person. the modal verbs that have no personal inflexions. Because of this “would” has also no personal inflexions.

5. The blanket socks were worn through in places, and his feet were raw and bleeding. His ankle was throbbing, and he gave it an examination.

Were- Verbal lexeme in plural form in the past Indefinite tense. The verb were has separate forms in the Past Indefinite to indicate person. In this sentence it comes with The plural noun which is socks. It belongs to second subsystem of the category of person. In this sentence passive voice was made up by means of verbal lexeme “were”.

His-Possessive determiner. It showed distinctions in person in this sentence. “His” is placed in front of the noun “ankle”.

Was-Verbal lexeme in singular in the past tense. In this sentence it comes with the noun “ankle” and the verb “throbbing”. It is second subsystem of the category of person. The verb has separate forms in the Past Indefinite to indicate person. In this sentence Past continuous tense was made up with the help of verbal lexeme “was”.

He-third-person singular.

6. As he rolled over on his elbow he was startled by a loud snort, and saw a bull caribou regarding him with alert curiosity.

He-third-person singular.

Was- Verbal lexeme in singular in the past tense. In this sentence it comes with the noun “elbow” and the verb “startled”. It is second subsystem of the category of person. The verb has separate forms in the Past Indefinite to indicate person. In this sentence passive voice was made up with the help of verbal lexeme “was”.

His-Possessive determiner. It showed distinctions in person in this sentence. “His” is placed in front of the noun “elbow”.

7. There were no trees, no bushes, nothing but a gray sea of moss scarcely diversified by gray rocks, gray lakelets, and gray streamlets. The sky was gray. There was no sun nor hint of sun.

were- Verbal lexeme in plural form in the past Indefinite tense. The verb were has separate forms in the Past Indefinite to indicate person. It belongs to second subsystem of the category of person.

Was-Verbal lexeme in singular in the past tense. It is second subsystem of the category of person. The verb has separate forms in the Past Indefinite to indicate person.

8. Soon he would come to the land of the little sticks. He felt that it lay off to the left somewhere, not far -- possibly just over the next low hill.

He-third-person singular.

Would- In this sentence “would” comes as the auxiliary verb and modal verb. While “would” can be used with all the persons. It refers to first subsystem of the category of person. The modal verbs that have no personal inflexions. Because of this “would” has also no personal inflexions.

9. He could hide it under his two hands. He knew that it weighed fifteen pounds, -- as much as all the rest of the pack, -- and it worried him. He finally set it to one side and proceeded to roll the pack.

He-third-person singular.

Could-modal verb and it refers to first subsystem of the category of person. In this sentence “could” comes as the auxiliary verb. “Could” is the past form of modal verb “can”

It-third-person singular.

10. He picked it up hastily with a defiant glance about him, as though the desolation were trying to rob him of it; and when he rose to his feet to stagger on into the day, it was included in the pack on his back.

He-third-person singular.

It-third-person singular.

were-Verbal lexeme in plural form in the past Indefinite tense. The verb were has separate forms in the Past Indefinite to indicate person. In this sentence it comes with The noun "desolation". It belongs to second subsystem of the category of person. In this sentence Past continuous tense was made up by means of verbal lexeme "were".

Was- Verbal lexeme in singular in the past tense. It is second subsystem of the category of person. The verb has separate forms in the Past Indefinite to indicate person. By means of the verbal lexeme "was" passive voice was made up.

11. If the man ran, he would run after him; but the man did not run. He was animated now with the courage of fear.

He-third-person singular.

Would- In this sentence "would" comes as the auxiliary verb and modal verb. While, "would" can be used with all the persons. It refers to first subsystem of the category of person. the modal verbs that have no personal inflexions. Because of this "would" has also no personal inflexions.

Was- Verbal lexeme in singular in the past tense. It is second subsystem of the category of person. The verb has separate forms in the Past Indefinite to indicate person. By means of the verbal lexeme "was" passive voice was made up.

12. It was unreasonable that he should die after all he had undergone

He-third-person singular.

It-third-person singular.

Was- Verbal lexeme in singular in the past tense. It is second subsystem of the category of person. The verb has separate forms in the Past Indefinite to indicate person. By means of the verbal lexeme "was" passive voice was made up.

Should- In this sentence "should" comes as the auxiliary verb. Moreover, should can be used with the first person. In contrast, In this sentence it comes with "he" which is the third-person pronoun.

13. When he finally gained his feet, another minute or so was consumed in straightening up, so that he could stand erect as a man should stand.

He-third-person singular.

His-Possessive determiner. It showed distinctions in person in this sentence. "His" is placed in front of the noun "feet".

Was- Verbal lexeme in singular in the past tense. It is second subsystem of the category of person. The verb has separate forms in the Past Indefinite to indicate person. By means of the verbal lexeme "was" passive voice was made up.

Should-as the auxiliary verb and modal verb. Moreover, should can be used with the first person. In contrast, In this sentence it comes with "he" which is the third-person pronoun. It refers to first subsystem of the category of person. Because it comes as a modal verb in this sentence.

Could-It refers to first subsystem of the category of person. In this sentence "could" comes as the auxiliary verb and modal verb "Could" is the past form of modal verb "can".

14. How could he have the laugh on Bill if that were Bill; if those bones, so pinky-white and clean, were Bill?

Could- modal verb and it refers to first subsystem of the category of person. In this sentence “could” comes as the auxiliary verb. “Could” is the past form of modal verb “can”. With the help of “could” question sentence was made up.

Were- Verbal lexeme in plural form in the past Indefinite tense. The verb were has separate forms in the Past Indefinite to indicate person. In this sentence it comes with “Bill”. It is second subsystem of the category of person.

15. So much of the game will be gain,

Though the gold of the dice has been lost."

Will- auxiliary verb. In this sentence it comes in the future tense and it comes with the noun “game”. In the positional use of will specifically marking the first person.

Conclusion

By making deep research and studying the topic “The category of person in English grammar “ I got chance to learn more and somehow revise it. I can say that while I was doing course paper, I learned a lot of information regarding the topic “The category of person. At first, I got into trouble, but I did this deep research work myself.

It should be admitted that writing course paper was somehow difficult because I had not experienced writing it before. Moreover, it was very useful for me. So, having worked this deep research I met so much information about grammatical person. For example:

Person is a category used to distinguish between those speaking, those being addressed, and those who are neither speaking nor being addressed. These three categories are called the first person, the second person, and the third person.

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